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Dosimetry analysis of different planning techniques of whole breast radiotherapy

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Background: Radiotherapy of the breast is an integral part of treatment of breast cancer, with the aim to achieve coverage of treatment volume but reduce dose to organs at risk as low as possible.

Currently, radiotherapy offers different planning and delivering techniques: three dimensional conformal techniques (3DCRT), intensity modulated radiotherapy (IMRT) and Volumetric Modulated Arc technique (VMAT). The aim of this work is to compare and analyze dosimetrically all planning techniques.

Methods and materials: Left sided whole breast patient was randomly selected for the purpose of the comparison. Four different plans were generated on the same set of structures, namely: 3DCRT plan, IMRT plan, and two VMAT plans: with partial continuous arcs and with arcs mimicking tangential gantry angles having avoidance sectors producing dosimetric "butterfly" effect. The plans were generated in treatment planning Eclipse v.15.6. Comparison of coverage, doses to OARs and low dose regions were analyzed.

Results: Prescribed dose was 40 Gy/15 fractions. The table below shows comparative data for target and organs at risk.

The coverage as well as maximum doses to the target have increased for advanced techniques, while homogeneity has significantly improved for advanced techniques deliveries. Volume of healthy tissue was highest for 3DCRT, while high dose volumes of target were higher for advanced techniques.

All three inverse planning methods led to an increase in low dose volume (V_5 and V_{10}) of the ipsilateral lung, opposite lung, and heart in comparison with 3DCRT, where only volume of lungs on the beam path was irradiated, with low dose region sharply cut at the beam edge. Mean lung dose is higher for advance techniques. Low dose volume of the contralateral breast and heart is higher for advanced techniques.

Total MU is highest for IMRT (3 fold than 3DCRT), which increases probability of backscatter in the body and gives additional dose to the tissues.

Discussion and conclusion: PTV coverage, conformity and homogeneity, in VMAT/IMRT are more superior than 3DCRT. Techniques with tangential field arrangement resulted generally in better OARs dosimetry compared to IMRT/VMAT.

Still, information on out of field dose is missing; low dose regions- volumes of 5Gy and 10 Gy are increasing in modulated techniques. This might have impact in secondary cancer induction in 10-15 years in patients < 40 years (at greater risk). Also liver toxicity should be taken into consideration due to increased number of modulated fields, greater scattering and dose leakage.

Important task in future months would be to develop algorithm for decision making on technique to be applied in individual cases, and decide who exactly benefits from modulated techniques. Careful selection of patients should be our next step.

Keywords: Breast cancer, VMAT, IMRT, 3DCRT, dosimetry, OAR, Medical physics

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